

Advice by the precursor EDIH network

Informal suggestions from the DIHNET precursor EDIH network on the further development of the EDIH network and Digital Transformation Accelerator

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0 Executive summary on the advice

The report is developed within the framework of the DIHNET project but in strong collaboration by the informal and open DIHNET precursor EDIH network initiated in October 2020. The report provides suggestions towards the European Commission for the further development of the EDIH network.

The overall conclusion from the activities of the precursor network is that EU-collaboration is crucial and there is a strong willingness from the community to actively participate and make it a success. The precursor network suggests that the collaboration can be organized in three layers of organization:

1. Actual EDIH-EDIH collaborations, based on corridors
2. Goal oriented subnetworks, using existing EU-networks as foundation
3. The overall initiation and forging of collaborations by the DTA

The three levels are accompanied by different business models. In these three levels, the actual creation of value and the way the value is capitalized is fundamentally different.

The report outlines 11 main suggestions, which could further develop the EDIH strategy and support collaboration. Many of the suggestions relate to the coordination and organization of the EDIH network and the supporting activities of the Digital Technology Accelerators. Therefore, these could support the Commission services in further planning the connection between the EDIHs and the DTA as well as the future DTA in evaluating the needs of the candidate EDIHs. The 11 suggestions are:

1. Focus the activities of the DTA on setting the boundary conditions and initiating collaborations;
2. The approach to the EDIH network is to create European value, but ensure room for regional implementation;
3. A (database) marketplace has limited added value. Instead an active brokerage functionality is needed, where access to information is connected to active brokerage support;
4. A detailed map of supply and demand is needed to find complementarities, using a distributed collection mechanism with all EDIHs.
5. The EDIH network should be all inclusive for DIHs, but prioritize on supporting the EDIHs.
6. The DTA should be driven by the needs of the EDIHs and this should be institutionally embedded.
7. Organize the EDIH network in subnetworks, making use of existing other EU-networks.
8. Ensure the quality of the network, using a EDIH quality label. But make sure that this a pro-active constructive approach that allows a positive commitment of the EDIHs.
9. Clarify the use of funding instruments by EDIHs, focusing on how to deal with the EDIH network, the DTA activities and the interregional EDIH collaborations.
10. Develop formalized approaches to facilitate collaboration to make the operations more concrete, practical and efficient through economies of scale.
11. Utilize the EDIHs as a tool to implement strategic agendas, as they will be a pivotal structure in the regions for research, development, innovation and deployment.

1 Introduction

1.1 The precursor network to informally explore the EDIH network

This report is an **advice** from the informal **precursor EDIH network** to the European Commission for the further development of the EDIH strategy.

The precursor EDIH network was initiated by DIHNET in October 2020. It is an informal, open, voluntary network and includes over 60 potential EDIHs and other relevant organisations. Around 90 representatives and experts participated and contributed to the precursor meetings and discussions. Four working groups explored topics related to activities, business models, governance and organization and sand-box activities related to the EDIH.

The precursor network was initiated within the context of the coming Digital Europe Programme, announcing the financial support of up to **210 European Digital Innovation Hubs** (EDIHs) in Europe. Included in this strategy is also the support of this **network** of EDIHs by a **coordinator** that forges/boost their collaboration: The Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA).

The report has been developed within the framework of the **DIHNET project**, in close collaboration with a limited number of representatives of organisations that are developing a proposal to become an EDIHs. DIHNET includes a work package for post-project sustainability. In consultation with the Commission, DIHNET adjusted its activities to explore the creation of such a network and its coordinator. This was taken up by setting up an informal precursor network, in which organisations were invited to discuss this collaborative EDIH network and the DTA with regard to business models and organisation.

1.2 Interregional collaboration key to the competitiveness of Europe

The EDIHs are seen as an important instrument to boost regional capacities and support European collaboration. Where the **individual EDIHs** have a **local** function, the overall aim of the **EDIH network** is to enhance the European collaboration (the **EU function**). The following points are important arguments for the European collaboration:

- **Easy access to leading edge technologies and skills/expertise at European level**
The interregional collaboration makes available competences from individual regions to other regions, complementing their shortage (import/export). It also includes the interregional use of available capital intensive “state-of-the-art” infrastructures developed
- **Support and initiate new business opportunities**
To broaden and reinforce innovative markets by supporting access industry and research in other European regions. Allowing/supporting access to each other’s markets will enhance the competitiveness of the regional industries and new business creation, also facilitating the creation of pan-EU value chains.
- **Increasing the global excellence of European specialisms**
Joint/complementary development of specific advanced digital technologies will boost Europe global leadership. Access to a network will allow the individual members to deliver and deploy technologies in variety of sectors. Interoperability and combined regional markets will improve economy of scale and use of capacities and capabilities.
- **Using regional experiences to build pan-EU EDIH capabilities**
Best practices developed in one region can be used in others, mirroring successful setups and

use of new knowledge developed through participation in DEP activities. Also, less mature hubs can learn from more mature hubs (widening).

- **Increase the impact of public and private capital investments**
Collaboration and aligning regional, national and European investments in innovation, avoids duplication and reduces overhead. Available infrastructures will be better used/aligned, as well as interregional of the public support system.
- **The European Single Digital Market to grow champions**
Supporting further access to private funding at Pan-European level through collaborations between European regions will also further contribute to reaching the European Single Digital Market objectives and will facilitate the growth of European champions in the European green and digital transformation. European champions are key to generate fertile ecosystems across Europe for the benefits of all European start-ups and SMEs

To actually benefit from these opportunities, a network is needed that facilitates these collaborations.

1.3 The EDIHs: pivotal to connect all regions

Being “a single organisation or a coordinated group of organisations with complementary expertise, with a not-for-profit objective that support companies – especially SMEs and mid-caps – and/or the public sector in their digital transformation”,¹ EDIHs are seen as a key tool to provide access to technology testing and support of digital transformation in their region.

The objective of the Digital Europe Programme is to have approximately 210 EDIHs across Europe,² which will be able to address the digital transformation challenges faced by many regions and SMEs in Europe. Through the EDIHs, SMEs across Europe are expected to be supported with the deployment of advanced digital technologies. While the DEP highlights HPC, AI and cybersecurity as priority technologies, the EDIHs are expected to support the industry at large with the twin transitions – green and digital. They will provide providing industry and public sector with support on broader range of technologies. The EDIHs therefore are positioned as a key mechanism to reach industry and the public sector, offering support in their digital transformation.

The EDIHs will have an important function to **support the regional ecosystem**, strengthening the overall regional capacities and developing further specialization. But the EDIHs will also have an important function to **connect to European strengths and support EU-collaboration**. In this way, the capacities across Europe can be utilized and this will contribute to the overall European added value. This European function is especially crucial to the EDIH network and the DTA.

¹ European Commission (2021), “European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme: Draft working document 25 01 2021”, page 7.

² The foreseen distribution of funding of Digital Europe Programme for EDIHs in all MS is between 107 (min hubs) and 211 max. number of hubs (recommended) but is subject to adaptation once a final decision on the budgets have been taken. For more information, see European Commission (2021), “European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme: Draft working document 25 01 2021”, page 30.

1.4 Our view on the EDIH network

It is clear that the EDIHs will not act in a vacuum, but need to be embedded in the regional ecosystem and collaborate to ensure that the European added value can be achieved. To optimally organise this European network, we see three main elements of this network:

- **The individual EDIHs**, which will be selected and will provide services to SMEs and public sector in their local ecosystem. The EDIHs can also be seen as a stronghold and connection to the **local** innovation capacities, competence centres, etc.
- **The Network of EDIHs**. The connected individual EDIHs will provide opportunities to each other regions, learn from peers and access capacities and expertise in other regions.
- **The coordinating DTA**: The Digital Technology Accelerator will support the network, by providing tools, facilitating the collaborations, initiating joint activities.

Figure 1: View on the EDIH network

Our view on these three elements is provided in the following chapters.

2 Our view on the EDIH network

2.1 The of the network is to connect and align the regions

The **vision** for the **individual EDIHs** is that the support of digital transformation is mostly done in the regions. A close proximity and active participation in regional ecosystems is crucial to ensure an efficient and effective support of the industry in order to uptake the advanced digital technologies. The place-based characteristics of the region and the existing partnerships and regional networks will be key to this support. Also, the regional characteristic will shape the way this support is organised.

However, the overall **vision** for the EDIHs is that to optimally benefits from advanced digital technologies, a strong **European collaboration** is needed to use the regional/national public investments and place-based capacities/capabilities. This collaboration will lead to a more competitive European industry, keeping regional specialisms, but making these regional capacities and specialisms available on European level and generating new European added value. This mechanism that regional specialisms can strengthen the European industry at large, is not only crucial for competitiveness, but also for other “grand challenges”, because of the enabling character of advanced digital technologies.

So, the **mission** of the **European EDIH network and member EDIHs** is to ensure that the benefits of interregional, European collaboration on digital transformation is cashed in. The EDIH network then ensures that available capacities/capabilities within regions are made available for other regions, as well as that their regional needs can be fulfilled by capacities/capabilities from other regions. The underlying EDIHs then are the gateway from/to other regions. Also, it is the mission of the collective EDIHs and its network to improve the interoperability of European public services, industrial digital solutions and digital skills.

We see the following **objectives and added value** as key to the **EDIH network**:

- A joined/aligned communication on European activities, leading to a **better awareness** on the benefits of advanced digital technologies and added value of European collaboration;
- Creating more impact by enabling the **pan-European use of state-of-the-art** European and regional infrastructures and expertise.
- Enhance the **quality of the European innovation ecosystem**, allowing (initiation of) EU-collaboration to be easier.
- **Initiating/enhancing the number of** actual interregional research/industry/government **collaborations** through pro-active brokerage.
- **Enhancing the regional quality of the support** of digital transformation by peer-to-peer learning and sharing best practices between the individual EDIHs.
- **Increased availability of skills in Europe** through increased access to regional available skills and joined development of skills and expertise;
- **Better access to finance** for interregional collaborations on digital transformation by increased (public and/or private) financial support.
- Support to creating **sustainable corridors** of collaboration between different regions and reducing the barriers for interregional and EU collaboration.

2.2 Specialisation to ensure attraction

The EDIHs all have their specialism. These specialisms are based on their regional strengths, their place-based (regional) research and industry capabilities as well as their own regional innovation ecosystem. Although the primary function of the EDIHs is local, the EDIHs improve their specialisms to both strengthen their region, as well as increase their added value to other regions. Using the specialisms as a USP, they stimulate the European smart specialisation. And attract collaboration!

Looking at the precursor network partners, most look at the specialisms as a combination between specific advanced digital technologies and a market demand (sectoral). Sometimes specific industrial/societal challenge is used to further demarcate the specialism. This is often based on the industrial characteristics of the region and existing research infrastructures/expertise.

An assessment of the precursor network partners (via a survey) specialism shows that this specialism is not easy to formulate and made operational. Many take a broad approach to formulate the specialisms, leading to a more inclusive approach. Focal areas are digitization in manufacturing, but also health and data management as well as connection to the twin digital and green transitions³.

Next to these specialisms, the focus of the activities of the EDIHs are on deployment. The DEP instrument is built around the need to get advanced digital technologies to business and this focus is highly appreciated. However, deployment needs to be founded in research and innovation. And therefore, most of the precursor network partners are based on existing research and innovation oriented DIHs (e.g. as the “orchestrator”), expanded with other regional partners that are complementary with e.g. the focus on deployment.

2.3 210 EDIHs; one European network

The dual function of the EDIH strategy on one side reinforces the region and on the other side strengthens European collaboration. So, the **network** aims at the actual collaborations between the individual EDIHs. The precursor network members see the following **key values created** by this collaboration:

- Access to expertise/infrastructures/markets;
- Access to funding for EU-collaborations;
- Creation of pan-EU value chains;
- Good/best practices of advanced digital technology deployment, as well as common standards, approaches, templates and background information;
- Access to available personnel/experts in other regions (workforce);
- Learning from each other with regard to approaches, infrastructures, best practices;
- Increasing impact through aligning investments.

³ These findings are subjective, as they are based on the limited number of members of the precursor network. Also, each EDIH is supposed to develop their own specialization based on regional capacities and needs and would therefore vary per market and technology.

An identification of the **contributions** that the EDIHs would be willing to provide, led to the following:

- Co-development joint approaches, sharing good practices and knowledge from own ecosystem;
- The collection of information about the strengths of the regions, including expertise and infrastructures;
- Financing EU-collaborations through a joint innovation voucher strategy to facilitate cross-border collaboration involving the regions;
- Active participation in periodic European EDIH networking events;
- Participate in brokering to boost interregional collaborations b/n regional industries and RO.

The selected EDIHs are also expected to develop their own focus – on a technology, application, market, or a combination. One way to promote the collaboration is to **create sub-networks** which connect EDIH with similar specializations and interest (in a technology or sector) to help exchange ideas and markets. Preferably, the connections should be non-competitive. Such organization in sub-networks will make interactions and collaboration more efficient and effective, while also supporting cross fertilisation. EDIHs will gain both on specific interactions at a sub-network level addressing their core activity, but they will gain also in meeting and interacting with other sub-networks to know better about challenges and expectations faced by other groups. Such dual approach could lead to new European Value proposition.

However, the existing DIHs that will not be selected as EDIHs are still an important part of the community and should be offered access to the EDIH network. They will also be interested to make use of the value of the network and are willing to contribute.

2.4 The DTA: Making sure the network works

The precursor network members stress that to transform the 210 individual EDIHs to a EDIH network requires a coordinating organization. The DTA is seen as a crucial organisation to facilitate between the EDIHs and potential sub-networks to increase economy of scale and initiate the collaborations. Also, overarching, more general activities are to be conducted that increase the efficiency. However, they acknowledge that active participation from the EDIHs is needed and indication on the scale of such participation could support the candidate EDIHs in their application.

An important aspect of the DTA is that it should in general focus on setting the boundary conditions to EU-collaboration, but after a first initiation it should be serving the EDIHs and let the EDIHs take charge of the actual making operational of the collaborations.

An overview of the expectations of the potential EDIHs towards the DTA was provided via a survey.

Figure 2: Results from the precursor network survey (N=50) on the future activities of the DTA.

Assessment within the precursor network of the needs that EDIHs have with regard to this coordinator, identified the following needs:

- A common, joined information base that should have a good overview of the members to enable quick connections among EDIHs;
- Common, co-created approaches among the EDIHs and support to liaise with sub-networks in the EDIH network;
- Facilitate/provide boundary conditions and tools to enable the members to seek each other, thereby also facilitating the connection among various sub-groups in the network;
- Initiate connections between EDIHs in the initial stages of collaboration, including exploring the organization of the EDIH network and the possibility to establish sub-networks.
- Support for the EDIHs with access to knowledge on specific technologies (via centres of excellence in HPC, AI, cyber for instance);
- Support of the activities of EDIHs to connect to European infrastructures, for example by exploring sharing of data to develop artificial intelligence enabled products and services;
- Support, tools and mechanisms to facilitate further engagement of funding in their network including private funding. Possible connection with support to DIHs could also be explored if the EDIH network deems this as useful.

- Active networking, including 1) organizing EDIH brokerage events and matchmaking, 2) community building 3) enabling viewing the services of the EDIHs,
- Explore joint activities to support the collaboration and the end users – e.g. activities to organize pan-EU collaborative research or organizing pan-EU call (see below for more examples)

It was considered important that DTA needs to be independent (not industry owned, non-for-profit, not prejudiced on technology/country, etc), but also that the EDIHs need to have a direct influence on the activities of the DTA.

2.5 Build on existing networks in the European DIH community

The network of EDIHs and the DTA will co-exist in a community where DIHs, regional, national and pan-EU networks already exist. Therefore, discussions with the precursor network indicate that the EDIH network should be inclusive, finding ways to also connect to the existing DIHs. In this the, EDIHs could be a connection point to the remaining DIHs in the region (a role that still needs to be explored with the remaining DIHs). Further, a connection with existing networks (e.g. on AI, on agriculture, robotics, etc.) and their role in the collaboration needs to be explored.

Also, it should be highlighted that setting collaborations and establishing trust are time consuming and challenging. Therefore the EDIH network should leverage as much as possible and build on existing collaborations, networks, alliances, associations. The DTA should support the connection of the EDIHs to the other relevant EU initiatives on digital transition, such as EU and international alliances, associations and the partnerships developed under previously by the DIHs, H2020, and the upcoming Horizon Europe programme (EUROHPC, and other of the Digital Industry & space Cluster of HE). Especially the existing and upcoming Innovation Actions and Coordination Support Actions should also be connected to the EDIHs through the DTA.

3 Making the EDIH network operational

3.1 Challenges ahead

One of the main challenges ahead of the EDIH network is to connect and synchronise activities in the DIH and EDIH ecosystem. There are already many DIHs operating and participating in regional, national and EU networks. The EDIHs can be seen as additional entities (even though many of the candidate EDIHs are likely to be built around existing DIHs) in this ecosystem. They can act as a stronghold, representing the regional capacities and at the same time providing regional ecosystem with access to the EDIH network partners, but this requires recognition of such function on all levels.

The following challenges are seen to make an efficient and effective network operational:

- Connect to existing networks, tools and other actors in the EDIH network to ensure that existing activities are optimally used;
- A clear distinction between the roles and responsibilities between the different actors in the EDIH network.
- Create clear focus on what topics the Europe has added value can be beneficial and actual collaboration can be established (connecting local-Europe).
- Find sustainable business models to ensure that European collaboration creates value, but also that value is capitalized and funded.
- Establishing the mechanisms and common approaches among the EDIHs and creating a sense of trust and cooperation among the EDIHs.
- Making sure that the EDIH related activities create an impact, rather than a set of tools and approaches that are not fully accepted and used by the EDIHs.
- How to initiate the participation of the Member States in the EDIH network and DTA.

3.2 Business models to ensure sustainable collaboration

The collaboration between EDIHs are focused on creating added value and the network are committed to creating these collaborations. However, to have a sustainable collaboration requires a business oriented approach, with a balance between providing value and capitalizing the value. Although it was concluded that some public funding always will be needed, a more commercial approach needs to be incorporated. These business models will however be different for the network of EDIHs and for the individual EDIH-EDIH collaboration (possibly supported by the DTA). Even though the two are connected, the value proposition, revenue streams and even needs of the target audience are expected to vary. Further it should be explored whether sub-networks in the EDIH network should be explored and how they will be connected to the network and the EDIHs.

So, three levels of collaboration can be distinguished between:

1. Business models in which the individual EDIHs collaborate to provide direct services through interregional collaboration (paid by companies, public sector (as a direct customer) and regional authorities);
2. Associations of EDIHs (subnetworks) that exploit synergies (scale, efficiency) between its EDIH members and even other existing networks that create platform business (supported by EDIHs, companies and the EC);
3. Network coordination, facilitation (the DTA), mainly focused on the member EDIHs (paid by EC);

Business models accompanied with agreed upon revenue models (could also be tit-for-tat or in-kind) will be needed to provide some structure to the collaborations. In the precursor network it was discussed that the local EDIHs will most probably need to remain the contact point of the companies in order to preserve their position in the local ecosystem and provide service in close proximity.

It is important to notice that the bi and multi-lateral collaborations between the “210 EDIHs”, mainly aim to provide services to the peer EDIHs and their customers (SMEs, public sector) or (local) partners. The added value of such collaboration can be multi-faceted but mainly revolves around learning from good practices of other EDIHs, import/export of infrastructures, expertise and innovations. Possible revenue models include tit-for-tat, performance fees, commercial fees, etc. However, alternative transaction methods could be utilized (tokens, points, services). For instance, the DIH HERO project is currently exploring exchange of digital currencies and in Germany, an exchange of tokens with equivalent service/price is explored. When it comes to brokerage fees, SMEs may be willing to pay for brokerage (to local EDIH or even the DTA) provided that there is strong enough need.

It is likely that for the EDIH-EDIH node collaboration, the DTA will be able to provide support, moderate and enable the tools and rules of engagement for the collaboration – a good brokerage platform is essential, trust, confidence in the expertise. Yet, a big challenge remains on how to deal with liabilities among the different services providers (EDIHs, CC, companies) cross-border. Also, ensuring good quality of the services offered by the partner EDIHs and addressing biases towards only partnering with certain partners are challenges for the future network that need to be considered. One option to address this are period assessments of the EDIHs (based on objective criteria) as well as incentives to redress lack of collaboration (e.g. more benefits/support/visibility if EDIH cooperate with # of other EDIHs).

Moreover, a major condition for the sustainability of the EDIHs collaboration is to generate economic value both at EDIH level and especially at European level. DTA can initiate and coordinate EDIHs network to become operational and will have to be part of the discussion on value generation and relevant business models as previously listed previously (tit-for-tat and performance fees). DTA will need to support and provide relevant tools and mechanisms to enable value generation within EDIH network; possible activities could relate to defining relevant KPIs and monitoring the generated value and exploring and encouraging further funding options.

3.3 The organisation and governance

The organization and governance of the EDIH network and establishing a connection with existing initiatives would require a usable and practical approach in order to support the EDIHs and enable the stakeholders to detect opportunities for collaboration. With this in mind, the following elements should be taken into account:

- Inclusiveness The EDIH network should explore how to establish a coherent and effective interaction with other DIHs and existing networks in order to enable the DIH and EDIH community to support and cater for the vast number of SMEs and public authorities in Europe.
- Need to explore how the other existing networks and the DTA and EDIHs will collaborate, including exploring possible subnetworks in the EDIH network.

- Organization of the network in thematic sub-networks based on technology, sector, market specializations, then connected to the actual DTA. Several present Innovation Actions can be seen as candidates to organised these sub-networks.
- For the precursor network which can provide suggestions to the future DTA: involve also DIHs and other networks and start with a light structure.

3.4 Financial considerations

The financial aspect of both the EDIHs and the EDIH node interregional collaborations are an issue to consider. Some of the participants in the precursor network pointed that clarity and case studies on how EDIHs can offer services funded by other programmes (e.g. the DIH is also part of EEN, EIT or Interreg programme) without duplicating efforts but also properly report will be useful. Also, clarification of what the EU grants to EDIHs will be with regard to commercial services are needed.

An important other financial aspect to consider is the funding of interregional collaborations. It is unclear at this moment how these collaborations can be funded. The DTA should be facilitating the further development of a structured approach in which this can be made operational. This issue is also connected to the not-for-profit rule set out in the EDIH guidance and FAQ is as follows. Unless the DEP Model Grant Agreement differs substantially from H2020/HEU MGA, all EDIHs that are constituted as a consortium will, per definition, be unable to provide services on a commercial basis since any income generated will be deducted from the grant. The mixing of public and private money within the hubs will inevitably lead to substantial challenges vis-à-vis the legal framework and financial rules governing European grants. Basic contractual agreements between EDIHs constituted as consortia are not legally enforceable, given that the EDIH is not a legal entity.

3.5 Member States also as key stakeholders

As mentioned, the EDIHs will perform dual function: 1. The first is to **enhance the capacity/capability of the regions** to support digital transformation in their region and 2. The second is to **enhance the EU-collaboration**. For these, the EDIHs are expected to receive funding from both the Member States (or regions) and the EU (through DEP). The EDIHs therefore have two important stakeholders: the Member States which are interested in promoting the national and regional competitiveness and the EC, which is focused on creating scale and efficiency in order to support industry competitiveness. The EDIHs need to balance these interests well while also directly providing practical support to the SMEs. As balance does not come easily, it could be a recommendation to assign the cross-border networking to purpose-built topics and sub-groups.

4 Conclusions and suggestions for next steps

4.1 Overall conclusions

The overall conclusion of our work is that a strong willingness can be expected among the EDIHs to commit and to be actively involved in European collaboration, supported by the DTA. This is driven by a strong acknowledgment that European collaboration is key to the survival of Europe's digital industry, as well as that it must be a joint venture among all EDIHs. We suggest to have a three-layered structure of the EDIH network:

- 1) The actual interregional collaboration that are initiated between individual EDIHs;
- 2) Goal-oriented (thematic: technology or application) sub-networks between EDIHs to exploit scale and synergy and how to create further value;
- 3) The overall initiating and forging of collaborations in a network by the DTA.

These three layers have their own business models and structure, but are intertwined in their operation. The layers should also ensure that the connectivity and operation run smoothly.

Our vision is that the DTA plays a crucial role in setting the boundary conditions for the EDIHs and other stakeholders to benefit from each other's capacities, capabilities, knowledge and experiences. The DTA could also recommend tools and process to the stakeholders to ease the communication and collaboration and operations of the EDIHs. But the regional sovereignty needs to be secured, allowing the EDIHs to benefit optimally and adapt to the local needs and stakeholder requirements. Reducing barriers for collaboration, economy of scale for joined activities, providing information about the strengths of Europe are all seen as added value from the network. One of the pre-requisites of the collaboration is to enable better understanding of each other's expertise, capabilities, capacities, services and focus areas.

So, the actual value for Europe is created by the individual EDIHs at large and therefore it is crucial to ensure that they have an active role in the DTA. Also, the collaboration with other EU-networks need to be ensured to make use of existing values. Even the link or involvement of non-EDIH stakeholders should be ensured, creating an all-inclusive network. But European added value requires that the network evolves towards a structure in which the value created is recognised and awarded by the regional ecosystems.

It is clear that in the early years of the EDIH network, governmental support is crucial and may be needed throughout the lifetime of the EDIHs and the network. Creating these collaborations is difficult and requires exploration towards standardized, efficient approaches. Also establishing trust, active networks, a position in the European innovation ecosystem takes time. However, after its initiation the EU-collaborations need to also have enough value to be capitalized in non-public ways, possibly still with support from public funding. We also believe that in the end, even if limited, public funding support will be needed to ensure that the overall ecosystem is supported (societal mission) and ensure an efficient and effective EU-collaboration so Europe can benefit from our regional strengths. Such next step toward sustainability will have to be designed from the launch of the EDIHs network activities with the support of the DTA.

4.2 Focus of the DTA should be on initiation

It is suggested that the **DTA should focus on supporting and initiating EU-collaboration, leveraging on the EDIH support**. For this, specific activities from the DTA will need to be organized but also the support of the EDIHs will be needed. It is suggested that clarification on the resources that the EDIHs are expected to dedicate as well as the connection among the EDIHs and the DTA are clarified to help the candidate EDIHs in their preparation for the restricted call.

The DTA will especially address collaboration between EDIHs, but the active engagement and initiation of the EDIHs will be needed to form the EDIH-EDIH collaboration. While the DTA and the network itself will need to develop and provide many services, in the short to medium term, it is suggested to focus on:

- Organize the enablers for EDIHs to find each other. This should connect to the previously discussed brokerage, mapping & positioning of the EDIHs, including an agreed taxonomy/ontology and possibly information on how the national EDIH/DIH environment is organized in the different MS.
- Stimulate and enable the EDIH-EDIH interaction, but organizing opportunities to share ideas and good practices on possible cooperation. Also continuous exploration of new approaches for cooperation should be organized.
- Develop and provide opportunities to discuss and co-develop with the EDIHs strategic and long-term vision and plans for the DIH/EDIHs policy in general and to support the EC digital and green strategy.
- Encourage cross fertilization between EDIHs sub-groups to generate new value proposition for exploitation of technologies and to address applications challenges.
- Provide information and connection with experts on particular tech/pillars of DEP
- Link to existing and upcoming networks and DIHs and identify a good governance (see below)
- Support the establishment of rules of collaboration (standard contracts, pricing/tokens/time exchange, etc).
- The DTA could support EDIHs in defining and implementing relevant tools and mechanisms for EDIHs to further engage public funding and private investment.
- DTA could support EDIHs to share good practices and implement recommendations from EIB on access to finance for (E)DIHs in: exploring dedicated debt instrument for digitalisation and exploring dedicated instruments (equity and/or debt for growth capital) for transformative technologies.

4.3 Create European value, but leave room for regional implementation

The EDIHs have a double function: 1) Increasing regional capacities and 2) Gateway to Europe. While coordination on EU level is seen as beneficial, the actual support to the industry and the public sector will mostly happen on the regional level. Therefore, we think it is crucial to **balance European coordination and making it operational on regional level**. The DTA and other European coordinating activities should be setting boundary conditions and more general structures for interregional collaboration, exchange and interoperability, but allowing the actual last step towards the customer to be tweaked for the regional customers. This is needed to adjust to the regional needs, but also to ensure that the EDIHs can create their individual brand that is crucial for their long-term sustainability.

4.4 Create an active brokerage functionality to forge collaborations

To enable EU collaboration among the EDIHs, it is crucial for the EDIHs to be able to find each other and the particular competences and specializations on the other EDIHs. Although there is often discussions about creating only a marketplace (passive), we think its actual benefits would be limited. Instead, the members of the precursor network believe that the creation of an active brokerage functionality would be more beneficial and critical.

To make this operational, it should include two elements. The first is a brokerage platform, in which the EDIHs can showcase demand and supply, underpinned by a systemic and well-organized mapping of the EDIHs and their competencies. The generic platform can be provided and maintained by the DTA but the EDIHs and the subnetworks should be engaged in developing, maintaining and providing the information in agreed taxonomies/ontologies. But the second is that a brokerage service is provided by the DTA in collaboration with the subnetworks that actively support the EDIHs to initiate the collaboration using the strategic information provided. Based on the discussions in the precursor network the following elements were identified as important:

- **focus on usability to find other EDIHs:** while simplicity is desired, the platform should also provide exhaustive enough information on the DIHs to help them identify partners
- **organize detailed mapping:** well-structured but detailed mapping of key aspects for the EDIHs is needed to allow to easily find partners. A balance should be found between making the mapping general enough to be easily used and extensive enough to cover all the aspects of the EDIHs.
- **link to existing domain/technology market places:** there are already a number of market places where DIHs are required to add information. Interoperability needs to be organised or alternatively a 1-time import of data from the present platforms to the new one could be explored.
- explore **linking to existing platforms**, including a systematic discovery of relevant platforms such as the EEN platform which offers a way to post requests towards service providers across Europe.
- **human communication and support** will be needed to complement the brokerage platform: establishing trust among the partners takes time and there will likely be a need for further support in events or one-on-one by the DTA to activate the connections.
- **ensuring connections and active collaborations:** many platforms and marketplace already exist. The DTA and its partners will have to identify and stimulate drivers for collaborations facilitating the use of the different tools set-up. Such drivers and triggers will contribute to the value generation process at local and pan European level.
- **Explore ways to improve the interoperability of European public services** and cross-learning from available solutions for the public administrations

Setting such a brokerage place is a project on itself with significant management and data protection (sensitivity) challenges. Yet, it can be seen as a long-lasting tool needed for the collaboration.

4.5 Create a detailed map of supply and demand and to find complementarities

Highly connected to 4.4 is the creation of a structured approach (taxonomy) to map the EDIHs. This is required to enable cooperation, a good overview of the capabilities of the different EDIHs is needed. It allows creation of a detailed positioning of the EDIHs and map of the supply and demand.

This requires **agreement on taxonomies/ontologies** that would allow finding the right partners. Some of the suggestions in the precursor networks discussion included: information on technologies,

sectors, markets, position in the value chain, end-market, vs technology orientation, infrastructures, information on the national DIH-EDIH landscape. Again, aligned with other existing mapping activities.

To maintain such information up to date, rethinking **the management of the mapping/information** is needed. One option is to have distributed management responsibilities to ensure up-to-date information and easy communication. There is also a need to implement processes to ensure that the information on this mapping of the EDIHs is up to date, trustable and accurate. A balance needs to be found between easy to update system and a process to ensure good quality of the data. The EDIHs and the suggested subnetworks can play a role in both requirements.

Yet, during the discussions, it was noted that next to the mapping of the EDIHs, further measures to stimulate the collaboration and networking, including ensuring that collaboration with different partners to prevent searching for partnership only with west EU for instance, is needed.

The previously mentioned development of the mapping of EDIHs **could be connected to the existing JRC Catalogue**. However, to enable EDIH brokering and inter-regional collaboration, the information collected is at this moment suboptimal. Therefore, it should be explored whether the extra functionalities to enable collaboration could be organized via the Catalogue. Also, possibilities for a restricted access section which allows monitoring of KPIs of the EDIHs could be explored.

Next to this, the collection of information and population of the catalogue should be changed towards a distributed mechanism in which the EDIHs play a crucial role in the data collection. The DTA then should coordinate and organise the validation of the data collected, including e.g. through delegation to the subnetworks.

4.6 Be all inclusive for DIHs, but prioritize EDIHs

The EDIHs are expected to be at the core of the EDIH network, cooperating in order to improve information exchange and collaboration among them. However, there is a need to also **include other DIHs in this collaboration**. This is essential in order to also define the different responsibilities of the core EDIH members and other stakeholders of the European DIH community.

Based on the discussions in the precursor network WGs, it is **recommended that the network should in general be inclusive**, in particular towards **(existing) DIHs**. DIHs are already existing and will continue to serve the local needs. Therefore, alignment and cooperation with them is important. EDIHs could serve as a regional connection to other DIHs but not in all cases as not all DIHs will accept such 'authority' over them. Further, **connection with existing networks** (CSAs, AI DIH network, robotics, etc) and finding synergies with them should be established. This is crucial not only to optimally benefit from existing structures and approaches to create added value for the regions, but also to make use of existing valuable capacities/capability. It will also contribute to share lessons learnt and best practices between activities having different roles but sharing common objectives for the digitization of the European industry. Next to this, both the DEP and Horizon Europe will also support existing and new networks.

To enable such inclusive network, there is a need for:

- Mapping of relationships, synergies and differences between EDIHs and other similar hubs and entities; For this common taxonomy will be needed

- Define a clear structured approach for the collaboration, looking at the roles and responsibilities of these networks and initiatives.
- Coordination from the DTA. This will be important as it could provide a platform to enable the collaboration as well as identify the responsibilities among the various members.
- Low threshold for participation could stimulate the inclusiveness, allowing existing initiatives to hold onto their brand and developed strategies.

4.7 Ensure institutionally that the DTA is driven by the needs of the EDIHs

The DTA is currently envisioned as a separate support mechanism which will help the EDIHs to network and learn from each other, including activities on train-the-trainer and the connection with the specific objectives of the DEP. In this respect, the DTA can support a strategic long-term vision and new ways to collaborate among the EDIHs. The DTA should also support the links with other (financial) programmes and networks in Europe.

However, to ensure that the DTA is actually EDIH driven and responds to the needs of the EDIHs, it is suggested to explore how the EDIHs can be included institutionally in the management of the DTA in the future. This can have the benefits of improved alignment to the needs but also create a sense of ownership (and participation!) from the EDIHs as well as a generating a common European vision. Many options are possible, EDIHs could provide input to the DTA via advisory boards, via inclusion in the management team, election mechanisms for boards in the DTA, possible secondments, etc. This needs to be coordinated with the future EDIHs, EC and the national governments.

As there are many EDIHs, some kind of a rotation to share ideas and provide direction to the DTA can be explored. Continuity of the activities of the DTA can be ensured via the DTA core team (at the start set by the service contract). The EDIHs should also be expected to contribute (with time, ideas) in the development of common approaches, strategies, exchanges, etc. However a way to ensure that all contribute is crucial.

The discussions that took place in the Working Group 3 about the governance of the Precursor Network led to the conclusion that the network should include different types of members:

- EDIHs as core members;
- DIHs as associated partners;
- Existing networks such as SmartAgriHub, EUhubs4data, EUrid... as associated partners

The Precursor Network can be seen as a start, exploring how the connections with such networks can be established. The Precursor networks has started contact with other existing networks that would like to collaborate with this approach, such as SmartAgriHubs, Rodin, I4MS or EUH4D (BigData).

4.8 Organize the network in subnetworks

The future EDIH network is expected to have about 210 EDIHs. Subnetworks with specific focus are a useful concept in between EDIHs and DTA to give as much priority to EU collaboration as to the regional competitiveness. To ease the communication and increase the chances of collaborations, discussions in the precursor network indicated that:

- **forming thematic EDIH sub-networks** should be explored in order to ease the connection among (E)DIHs with similar specialisms. EDIH-EDIH collaboration is expected to be sector/application or technology driven, therefore such networks can provide a common ground among the EDIHs.
- The organization in sub-networks should be **coordinated by a specific organization/project** which then interacts with the DTA to align messages and exchange information.
- The **DTA can then orchestrate the sub-networks as well as the more general topics** on collaboration as well as facilitate the organizational and administrative side of organizing such sub-networks

4.9 Ensuring quality of the network and EDIH quality label

The EDIHs will undergo a selection process in order to be granted the EDIH label. It is however crucial to explore how to **establish an EDIH quality level**, potentially indicating different levels. To establish a collaboration, there should be some kind of quality assurance of the services offered also by the other partners in the EDIH network. This quality will initially be provided by the selection process.

During the precursor network discussions, it was suggested that **periodic checks based on previously agreed and very objective criteria** could be a solution. This evaluation can potentially be organized by the DTA (as a neutral body) but clarity of the criteria, objectivity of the results and ease of collection of the information should be ensured. It should however be mentioned that not all precursor members agree with this approach as it might lead to more complexity. Whether additional actions are required should be further explored by the future DTA.

The added value of this evaluation is not only to ensure a quality mechanism, but also drives the further development of the EDIHs. It will structure the development of training programmes, as well as initiate the participation of EDIHs in training programmes.

4.10 Clarify the use of funding instruments by EDIHs

The EDIHs are expected to be funded via the DEP programme and the national/regional funds. However, it should be clarified on EU level, what funds could be used for what activities and how the funds will be distributed (following the EIT approach?). Discussions in the precursor network also indicated that clarification is needed on how the reporting will be organized (single reporting mechanisms of the EDIHs in DEP vs reporting for the different co-funding sources). Further it will be worth clarifying how the EDIHs can use their funding and complementary programmes such as ERDF HE, Invest EU, to directly provide services to the local SMEs.

Special attention is requested for the funding of the interregional collaborations. As the funding of the EDIHs primarily are allocated to the financing of the regional partners, the combined, interregional funding is to be addressed (e.g. funding of joined interregional projects).

4.11 Develop formalized approaches to facilitate collaboration

To enable EDIHs to easily and quickly exchange services among each other, it is suggested that a **standardised contractual arrangement is explored by the future EDIH network**. As suggested in the precursor network discussions, the future DTA could explore a system of services and value for the different services (exchanged between the EDIH-EDIH collaboration). Templates could be provided.

This could lead to a comparatively easier exchange of service/type of payment between EDIHs, avoid individual contracting.

The exchange of services does not necessarily need to follow money exchange. Exchange of tokens, points, time could be explored. This should relate to the services between the two EDIHs. For the service directly provided to an SME, the SME could pay (if payment for these services is needed and not provided for free by local DIH).

4.12 Utilize the EDIHs as a tool to implement strategic agendas

The EDIHs are expected to have close connection to the regional needs and stakeholders as well as support the European added value via collaboration. As such, they are well positioned to support industry and the regional ecosystem in the implementation of strategic priorities (new technologies, more sustainable, green economy, etc) and help companies understand and adopt these.

Annex: Overview of the participating organisations in the open precursor network (as of 8 March 2021)

No	Proposed (E)DIH and other participating organizations	Region	Country
1	IP4FVG	Friuli Venezia Giulia	Italy
2	BDIH	Basque country	Spain
3	EDIH SMITZH	The Rotterdam-The Hague Area	Netherlands
4	NND	Northern Holland region	Netherlands
5	EDIH SNL	Noord-Brabant, Zeeland	Netherlands
6	Crobohub	Croatia	Croatia
7	Smart Attica EDIH	Attica Region	Greece
8	Transilvania DIH	Transilvania	Romania
9	Latvian IT cluster	Latvia	Latvia
10	EDIH4IAE.LT	Central and Western Lithuania	Lithuania
11	Minasmart	Auvergne Rhône Alpes	France
12	DIH Tourism 4.0 CZ		Czech Republic
13	L-hub	Luxemburg	Luxemburg
14	DigiT Hub	Skåne-SW	Sweden
15	Flanders Make	Flanders	Belgium
16	EDIH Robosence	Eastern Netherlands	Netherlands
17	EDIH Saxony	Saxony	Germany
18	Extremadura digital Innovation Hub Tech4E	Extremadura	Spain
19	AIR4S DIH	Madrid	Spain
20	Flanders' Healthtech Hub	Flanders	Belgium
21	AI DIH network	EU	European Union
22	Cybersecurity Innovation Hub	Brno/Jihovýchod	Czech Republic
23	DIHGIGAL	Galicia	Spain
24	DIH Región de Murcia	Murcia	Spain
25	Grand E-nov	Grande Est	France
26	Czech Southwest DIH	Jihozápad/Severozápad	Czech Republic

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27	Digital Hub Logistics Dortmund	Regierungsbezirk Arnsberg, Northrhine-Westfalia	Germany
28	i4CAM HUB	Castilla-La Mancha	Spain
28	i4CAM HUB	Castilla-La Mancha	Spain
29	HPC4Poland EDIH	Wielkopolska	Poland
30	IRIS DIH	Navarra	Spain
31	Inndromeda DIH	Valencia	Spain
32	MADE	Lomerdia/national	Italy
33	Aragon DIH	Aragón	Spain
34	DIHNAMIC	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	France
35	CSEM		Switzerland
36	IMEC	Flanders	Belgium
37	DigiTech	Sofia	Bulgaria
38	DIHBIO	Madrid	Spain
39	EDIH AURORA		Norway
40	Zealand Hub		Denmark
41	Balearic Islands DIH	Palma de Mallorca	Spain
42	DIVA -Digital Innovation Value Accelerator	Pays de la Loire	France
43	DIH Marche	Ancona	Italy
44	DIH Silesia Smart Systems	Katowice	Poland
45	DIH5G		Poland
46	iMan Norte Hub		Portugal
47	Irish Manufacturing Research DIH		Ireland
48	ASTER DIH	Emilia-Romagna Region	Italy
49	SUMITY EDIH	Paris	France
50	DIH Confindustria Emilia-Romagna Ricerca	Emilia-Romagna Ricerca	Italy
51	Lithuanian Robotics DIH		Lithuania
52	Agrobofood		European
53	Institute of Entrepreneurship Development (IED)	Larissa	Greece
54	AddedValue DIH	Budapest	Hungary

55	am Lab		Hungary
56	BlueDIH		Croatia
57	DIH-HERO (IA)		European
58	EDIH Vilnius/Sunrise Valley DIH	Vilnius	Lithuania
59	DATAlife	Galicia	Spain
60	Digihall	Ile-de-France (Paris region)	France
61	Dutch Societal Innovation Hub	NL	Netherlands
62	NEDIH, ORION, MOSAIC		Norway
63	TICE	Portugal	Portugal
64	AsDIH (Asturias DIH)	Llanera	Spain
65	University of Belgrade - School of Electrical Engineering (ETF)/Belgrade robotics DIH		Serbia
66	Czech Institute of Robotics, Informatics, and Cybernetics/ Czech Technical University	Prague	Czech Republic

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